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QUALITY OF LIFE CHILDREN WITH FOOT DEFORMITIES MEASURED BY THE OXFORD ANKLE FOOT QUESTIONNAIRE FOR CHILDREN

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Abstract: The paper discusses the prevalence and impact of foot deformities in children, focusing on conditions like pes planus and pes cavus. Two main categories of foot problems are identified: deformities occurring in the fetal period and malformations during the embryological period, including metatarsus varus and clubfoot. The study emphasizes the importance of understanding children's quality of life (QoL), considering health-related QoL, social indicators, and subjective well-being. The Oxford Ankle Foot Questionnaire for Children (OxAFQ-C) is introduced as a tool to assess QoL in children with foot deformities. Research findings indicate significant differences in QoL between children with foot deformities and healthy counterparts, particularly in the physical, emotional, and social domains. The conclusion underscores the need for timely intervention to support children with foot deformities and highlights the crucial role of subjective well-being in overall QoL.

Keywords: Clubfoot, Metatarsus varus, Oxford Ankle Foot Questionnaire for Children (OxAFQ-C), Pes cavus, Pes planus, Quality of life (QoL)

1. INTRODUCTION

Foot deformities are a frequent diagnosis in outpatient clinic work. Based on research that investigated the frequency of foot deformities, we can see the trend of their growth. Postulating the hypothesis that the difference between a normal foot and a foot with a deformity does not exist, the frequency of the deformity occurs in about 40% of the student population, which indicates the seriousness of the situation. Emphasis is placed on foot arch deformities, pes planus and pes cavus. Pes planus occurs in the form of flexible and rigid flat feet. Pes cavus occurs in the form of anterior cavus foot, posterior cavovarus, pes calcaneovarus and pes equinovarus. Other, more serious deformities occur in a smaller percentage. [1], [2], [3]

Foot problems fall into two main categories:

- Deformities that occur in the fetal period, where the foot has a normal configuration.
- Malformations, which occur during the embryological period and lead to anatomical deformities. [4], [5]

The three most important childhood foot deformities are: metatarsus varus (metatarsus adductus), calcaneovalgus and talipes equinovarus, better known as clubfoot.

Most common malformations are: syndactyly, polydactyly, clinodactyly, macrodactyly and brachymetatarsalgia. [6]

Other malformations of the front part of the foot include hallux valgus, i.e. metatarsus varus primus, hallux flexus, congenital vertical talus, pathologies located on the nails. [4], [5], [6]

Some of the acquired toe deformities are hammertoes, clawed toes and clubbed toes, and are usually caused by wearing inadequate footwear.[6] These conditions can occur separately, but also as companions of certain diseases such as: spina bifida, cerebral palsy, Duchenne's muscular dystrophy, Charcot-Marie-Tooth disease, Friedrich's ataxia, and many others. [5]

Children's gait is observed from several aspects: while the child is walking normally, walking on toes, heels, sideways, while jumping, and finally while running. Through all these daily children's activities, we can assume how these deformities affect their QoL. [5]

2. CHILDRENS QUALITY OF LIFE

According to Flanagan, the quality of life (QoL) of children represents the freedom of children to play, learn, grow and mature in a safe environment, surrounded by love. [7], [8], [9]

Children with impaired QoL grow into adults with impaired QoL.

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They can not be compared to each other because for children and adults they are two differentially different terms. Children's QoL is assessed with three aspects:

- Health-related QoL (HRQoL)
- Social indicators
- Subjective well-being

When establishing the concept of measuring the QoL of children, the focus was exclusively on measuring the negative outcomes of morbidity and mortality. Based on United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, there was a change in the observation of QoL, and placing an emphasis on subjective well-being, and the child's right to have their decisions taken into account in these delicate matters. [10], [11], [12] This Convention also states that children have the right to adequate health care, education, proper nutrition, personality development and mental and physical potential. As they are a vulnerable group and depend on adults, it is up to the adults to provide them with all the listed items, so that with their help, the children can really experience an improvement in life in the way they understand it. The concept of children's QoL shows positive aspects for its improvement, children's wishes and their perspective on the world. [11]

HRQoL is related to the subjective feeling regarding one's health condition, disease, deformities and disabilities. Although there are many definitions of children's QoL, Eiser et al. (1999) define it as the difference between the actual and the desired self due to the consequences of illness. Very important domains from a child's perspective are free time, time spent at school and relationship with peers, self-confidence, self-image and family. [9], [12]

Questionnaires used to measure children's health-related QoL can be general (generic) and specific, in order to compare groups with or without diseases, as well as groups with different diseases. The most commonly used generic questionnaires are the Pediatric QoL questionnaires (such as KIDSSCREEN and The PedsQL). [10] Although this tests evaluate healthy children, the absence of disease does not necessarily mean that QoL is satisfactory because it is not only the absence of disease.

The original concept of social indicators was based on infant mortality, child vaccination, school attendance and education, tobacco and alcohol abuse, indicators of poverty within and outside the family, and its living conditions in it. The newer concept is focused on developing moral beliefs, behavior, and abilities in order to develop successful life development in children. [9], [10], [12]

Considering the individual, the sense of well-being appears to be the most important aspect of QoL. Roughly, it can be defined as a feeling of happiness and satisfaction with one's position in life. [10] In childhood and adolescence, it depends on self-confidence, social relations, stress, anxiety, loneliness, but also risky behavior. The most commonly used isolated scales for this aspect are: Perceived Life Satisfaction Scale, Student's Life Satisfaction Scale (SLSS), Multidimensional Students' Life Scale Satisfaction Scale-(MSLSS.) [10]

Speaking about children in general, in the research of Wallander and Knot (2015), emphasis was placed on social indicators and a sense of well-being, as more important aspects for children than health-related QoL. Physical impairments in children, especially at an early age, disrupt their integration into the environment and society. Children are also often concerned about how they look and behave in front of others. They often face ostracism from society due to fear of their condition, and teasing. [9], [10]

As previously stated, there are generic and disease-specific questionnaires for QoL assessment. Specific questionnaires have the ability to accurately detect the level of QoL in children with a specific musculoskeletal disorder, as well as the ability to assess changes over time in QoL. [13]

One such is the Oxford Ankle Foot Questionnaire for Children (OxAFQ-C) intended for children. It is designed so that the questions relate exclusively to problems with the ankle and foot, in the age group of 5-16 years. It is not stated how those problems occurred, whether due to disease, muscle or tissue injury, or neurogenic way, but only how that problem affects the child's life. [14]

It consists of questions that can indirectly lead to the conclusion of the child's QoL, although its direct purpose is not its assessment. It consists of three domains: school and play, physical activity outside of

play, and the child's emotional status, as well as a subdomain related to the shoes that children want to wear, that is, whether they are able to wear them. Each question is scored from 0-4, where 0 is the presence of pain, discomfort, dissatisfaction, etc. constantly present, and 4 never, which leads to the conclusion that a higher number of points reflects better child functioning and a better quality of life, and the questionnaire is filled out for a period of 7 days in the past. [14], [15], [16]

There are two types of this questionnaire, a version that is completed by children, and a version that is completed by their parents if they are unable to. Both types of questionnaires contain the same questions from the same domains already mentioned.

While constructing this questionnaire, a focus group was organized to determine which problems most often affect children aged 5-15 with diagnoses of cerebral palsy, congenital talipes equinovarus, flat feet, injured metatarsal bones and Marfan's syndrome.

They mentioned the following problems that affect their daily life: pain, swelling, fatigue, inability to play in the school yard, park, in physical education class, infrequent trips to school, difficulties in walking, running and going down and climbing stairs, inability to carry clothes and shoes they want, sadness, anxiety and feelings of exclusion. [17] As all these problems directly affect QoL and are not considered as a separate entity, the OxAFQ-C can be considered a questionnaire that detects children's QoL.

Research was found where OxAFQ-C from a QoL point of view was used in conditions such as polydactyly [18], talipes equinovarus [15], flat feet [19], [20]...

In research, the OxAFQ-C was used separately [14] or together with PedsQL [21], KIDSSCREEN-52 HRQOL [22] and the Kid's Inpatient Descriptive Life Satisfaction Scale-KINDL [20] in order to complement each other's results. [13], [15]. All conducted researches show significant deviations compared to children without the aforementioned deformities and malformations.

In the research of Kothari et al. (2015), where children with flat feet and healthy children were compared, a statistically significant difference was found in QoL and functioning in all domains, and mostly in the domain of physical functioning, then emotional, shoes they would like to wear and at the end of school and play. [19]

Dokhov et al. (2019) state that children with flat feet have a very pronounced dissatisfaction in the physical domain, as well as in the domain of footwear selection. It is considered that the emotional and school aspects are replaced by different requirements, i.e. easier tasks in physical education classes, as well as acceptance by friends and the environment. The KINDL questionnaire, which sought to compensate for the shortcomings of the OxAFQ-C questionnaire, also confirmed the most pronounced deviations in the physical domain and self-image. [20]

Hajebrahimi et al. (2020) tested children with talipes equinovarus, and the most threatened domain was physical, then emotional, and finally school and play. There are no data on satisfaction and the possibility of the desired footwear. [15]

Children with preaxial and postaxial dactyly showed an extremely worse QoL in all domains compared to the control group of healthy children, measured by OxAFQ-C, while PedsQL showed a significant difference in the physical domain. [18]

3. CONCLUSION:

Foot deformities represent a serious health problem for children, and their impact on the quality of life of children and their daily activities must not be neglected. Understanding and timely intervention are key to providing support and improving the well-being of children with foot deformities. Feeling of well-being, ie. subjective satisfaction and happiness play a key role in the quality of life of children. Physical impairments, especially in young children, can significantly affect their social interaction and emotional well-being. OxAFQ-C is a specific questionnaire that was not initially intended to test QoL, but contains items that refer to it, and researchers have successfully used it in its assessment. Research has shown significant differences in the quality of life between children with foot deformities and healthy children, with special emphasis on the physical aspect, emotional well-being and social interactions.

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